

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D9.1

Development and Demonstration of RM exploration service
(alpha version)

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DL	Deep Learning
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
HS	Hyperspectral
MERIT	Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain
ML	Machine Learning
MS	Multispectral
NIR	Near Infrared
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PI	Processability Index
SLIC	Simple Linear Iterative Clustering
SNIC	Simple Non Iterative Clustering
SOTA	State of the art
SR	Super Resolution
SWIR	Shortwave Infrared
T	Task
VH	Vertical Horizontal
VMS	Volcanogenic Massive Sulphides
VV	Vertical Vertical

XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
XRF	X-Ray Fluorescence

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The TERRAVISION project aims to boost sustainability and efficiency in the mining industry by using advanced Earth Observation (EO) technologies. It is designing an all-encompassing platform, linking satellite, airborne, and ground-based remote sensing data to support the whole value chain of raw materials from exploration to post-closure activities. Important goals of the project include modernisation of exploration activities, improvement of risk and hazard management, optimisation of extraction rates and guaranteeing environmental compliance. The report outlines the design and scope of the EO-based raw material exploration service that will be developed under the TERRAVISION project. This service will be designed to support both greenfield and brownfield exploration for regional, district, and target scales.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The primary goal of this report is to present the initial design and scope of the EO-based raw material exploration service. The service will enable multiscale prospectivity mapping, spanning regional, district, and target (deposit) scales, by integrating public geoscience datasets as well as advanced spectral and geophysical data acquired from spaceborne and airborne platforms. At the regional scale, geological maps and geochronological datasets will be combined with spaceborne geophysical data to guide early-stage greenfield exploration. For district and deposit scale exploration, the service will leverage high spatial resolution remote sensing data and automated analytical methods to fill the data gap in critical exploration parameters such as lithostructural features, hydrothermal alteration zones and the distribution of indicator minerals. Finally, this report outlines the status of the associated field sampling campaigns and introduces the initial framework of the Processability Index (PI), a novel spectral-based approach to evaluate the processing behaviour of ores based on their mineralogical composition.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

This report outlines the methodological framework that will be developed for raw material exploration across regional, district, and target scales, focusing on the required data and the automated mapping of critical parameters essential for mineral prospectivity mapping. The report also presents the initial design of the PI, marking a first step toward integrating processability behaviour into early-stage exploration models. Additionally, it summarises the field sampling campaigns conducted during the first 18 months of the TERRAVISION project.

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable, part of the Horizon Europe project TERRAVISION, focuses on describing the initial design of critical raw material exploration methods to support both greenfield and brownfield exploration, reduce exploration costs and risks, and facilitate data-driven decision-making.

In more detail, this report describes:

- The multiscale prospectivity mapping strategy for identifying new deposits in greenfield and brownfield areas.
- The public geoscience and spaceborne geophysical data to be collected and used as input features for prospectivity modelling.
- The automated methods for mapping critical exploration parameters at district and target scales for exploration, such as lineaments, lithology, indicator minerals, and hydrothermal alterations.
- The initial design of the PI for evaluating the processing behaviour of ores.
- The status of the field sampling campaigns.

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

- **Hierarchical multiscale prospectivity mapping** to support **greenfield** and **brownfield** mineral exploration.
- **Coarse spatial resolution** public geoscience and spaceborne geophysical data will be used for **regional-scale** prospectivity mapping.
- **Medium and high spatial resolution** geoscience data and maps of critical parameters, such as structural maps, indicator minerals and alteration maps extracted from multiscale spaceborne and airborne spectral data, will be used for the **district and target scale**.
- **Interpretable ML models** will be used to explain model predictions and improve the performance of prospectivity mapping.
- **Automated methods for lithology, indicator minerals, hydrothermal alterations and lineament mapping**.
- Characterisation of **ore processability** based on **spectral-based mineral composition** predictions.
- **Field sampling** has been already carried out at two mining sites.

1. Introduction

Securing sustainable access to critical raw materials is a key priority of the European Union (EU), underpinning both the European Green Deal and the EU Raw Materials Strategy. As Europe transitions toward a climate-neutral and digital economy, the availability of responsibly sourced raw materials has become increasingly important. In this context, remote sensing technologies offer a non-invasive, cost-effective, and scalable approach to mineral exploration, particularly valuable in underexplored or logistically challenging regions. These technologies support early-stage targeting by providing regional and local-scale geospatial insights that complement traditional exploration methods.

As outlined in WP9, the primary objective of Task 9.1 (T9.1) is to develop and implement EO-based methodologies for mineral exploration. This includes the acquisition and processing of spectral and geophysical data from airborne and spaceborne sensors, as well as the collection of field samples from the mining areas of the TERRAVISION demonstrators.

1.1 Deliverable Description

Initial version will focus on providing an overview of Raw Material Exploration Methods and Collection of Field Samples.

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

This document presents an overview of the methodologies that will be employed in the exploration of raw materials and the collection of field samples. It emphasises the integration of state-of-the-art (SOTA) techniques across regional, district, and target-scale mineral exploration for greenfield and brownfield areas. These include advanced and automated approaches for critical parameters and proxies essential for mineral prospectivity assessment.

Furthermore, the document outlines the current status of field sampling activities. It also introduces the initial design of the PI, a semiquantitative metric aimed at characterising ore processing efficiency through spectral-based mineral grade predictions.

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

1.3 Intended Audience

The dissemination level of this report is Public. It is specifically intended for the TERRAVISION demonstrators. This deliverable ensures that the participants are informed about the critical raw material exploration methods planned for development and deployment on the TerraFusion platform.

1.4 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

The sections following the introduction are an overview of the following approaches, which are going to be developed:

1. Mineral prospectivity mapping (Section **Error! Reference source not found.**)
2. Geological feature mapping (Section **Error! Reference source not found.**)
3. Processability Index (Section 4)
4. Field Sampling (Section 5)

2. Mineral Prospectivity Mapping

2.1 Introduction

The global demand for critical raw materials is projected to rise significantly in the coming decades, driven by population growth and evolving consumption patterns in the global economy (Lawley et al. 2022). Volcanogenic massive sulfide (VMS) deposits are key sources of copper, cobalt, silver, gold, lead, and zinc, which are essential metals for modern technologies and resilient supply chains. Additionally, celestine and magnesite deposits provide vital supplies of strontium and magnesium, respectively.

To address the challenge of securing future supply, the TERRAVISION Raw Material Exploration will enhance mineral prospectivity modelling for VMS, celestine and magnesite deposit types across multiple spatial scales, ranging from continent-wide evaluation to detailed target-scale assessments. These efforts will be based on the mineral systems approach (Wyborn and Jaques, 1994), leveraging an integrated framework that incorporates interpretable machine learning (ML) techniques and multiscale public geoscience datasets, as well as geophysical data, spaceborne, and airborne remote sensing data.

2.2 Methodology

The mineral systems approach (Wyborn et al., 1994) views mineral deposits as localised expressions of extensive geological processes that function across a wide range of spatial and temporal scales. These systems concentrate mass and energy through interconnected geological mechanisms, ultimately leading to the formation of mineral deposits. Central to this approach is a comprehensive conceptualisation and spatial integration of the ore-forming geological processes into four key components: sources, pathways, traps, and their translation into mappable targeting criteria.

The process of mineral prospectivity mapping, as well as decisions regarding targeting and ground selection, occurs on various scales and changes dramatically within each of these scale ranges. These range from broad regional ground selection to more specific choices at the camp or district level, down to the detailed definition of prospects and ultimately the identification of ore shoots within a prospect or deposit (Hronsky and Groves 2008). The importance of exploration criteria will vary across scales for two reasons: (1) the scale at which various critical processes of the mineral system operate, and (2) the availability of geoscience datasets that can help identify mappable targeting criteria across the entire project area (Mccuaig, Beresford, and Hronsky 2010).

As exploration narrows from regional to prospect scale, the emphasis shifts from broad system components (e.g., source) to those directly controlling ore localisation, such as traps and fluid conduits (Figure 1). At regional scales, few public and coarse spatial resolution geoscience datasets are sufficient for targeting, whereas finer scales require increasingly detailed and spatially precise geological datasets. These include high-resolution maps of lithology, structure, and alteration, though such data are rarely available before a discovery at the prospect scale for greenfield areas (Hronsky and Groves 2008).

Figure 1. The relationships between component processes across multiple scales (after Hronsky and Kreuzer 2019)

For this project, a multiscale mineral prospectivity mapping workflow will be structured to progressively refine exploration focus from regional to district and ultimately to deposit scale, in alignment with the principles of the mineral systems approach (Figure 2). The regional scale will encompass the entirety of Europe, providing a continental overview of broad prospective zones, which will indicate the extent of subsequent district-scale prospectivity mapping. The district scale will focus on specific metallogenic provinces associated with each deposit type: the Iberian Pyrite Belt for VMS deposits, the Granada Basin for celestine, and North Evia in Greece for ultramafic-hosted magnesite. At the target scale, analysis will be concentrated on mining areas and their immediate surroundings, as delineated by the district-scale prospectivity models. This hierarchical spatial structure ensures coherent scale integration and effective narrowing of exploration focus. This hierarchical framework ensures that geological understanding is incrementally improved and that predictive models become increasingly precise at each stage of exploration.

Figure 2. Left: Regional scale orogenic gold prospectivity map for the northern part of Finland (Niiranen et al. 2019); Centre: District scale gold prospectivity map of the Perapohja Schist Belt (Nykänen et al. 2017); Right: Target scale confidence levels assigned to prospectivity results and exploration targets (Chudasama et al. 2022a).

In practice, the methodology for each scale of the mineral prospectivity model will be based on three components: (1) the critical processes of the mineral system that operate at the relevant scale, (2) the availability of data with spatial resolution relevant to the scale of the

critical processes and (3) whether the prospectivity modelling is performed in greenfield or brownfields situations (i.e., availability of drill data, ground-based geophysical data, geochemical data) (Figure 3). Next, follows an overview of the design for each scale level (i.e., regional, district, deposit) of the prospectivity mapping methodology.

Figure 3. The methodology selected for each prospectivity scale level depends on the availability of data.

2.2.1 Regional Scale Prospectivity Mapping

At the regional scale, the objective is to identify broad zones of mineral potential by recognising all major components of the mineral system for each deposit type, including sources, pathways, traps, and outflow zones. This involves compiling and processing regional geological maps, as well as geophysical datasets such as satellite gravity and magnetic data, which serve as spatial proxies for the identified mineral system components and will be used as input features in ML models trained on known mineral deposits and occurrences.

The locations of known mineral deposits and occurrences, which will be used as labels during model training, are based on previously published compilations and updated inventories provided by EuroGeoSurveys and USGS. Potential input features for the model will be lithological and geochronological data from the 1:1 Million Pan-European (EGDI) Surface Geology. Fault data distribution can be taken from the GEM Global Active Faults Database (GAF-DB) which is the first public, comprehensive database of active faults with worldwide coverage (Styron and Pagani 2020). Lithospheric thickness maps can be acquired from (Hoggard et al. 2020). Proximity to passive margins and carbonaceous sedimentary rocks (e.g., black shales) maps are available from the global compilations of (Bradley 2008) and (Granitto et al. 2007). Additionally, global-scale spaceborne geophysical datasets and their derivatives, such as ESA's GOCE gravity data (Drinkwater et al., 2003) and ESA's SWARM magnetic data, can be used to test their relevance to the mineral systems being targeted. These datasets by no means represent an exhaustive list of the input features that will be used in the ML models. Additional datasets will be incorporated based on the conceptualisation of the mineral system

for each deposit type into interpretable ML models, such as random forests, and weight of evidence (WOE). Known mineral occurrences and deposits will be utilised to spatially validate conceptual mineral system models, highlight the geological parameters which are most predictive of mineralisation through feature optimisation techniques, and train the ML models. Additionally, the uncertainty in the regional-scale models will be addressed with methods such as ensemble modelling, Bayesian inference, or sensitivity analyses to assess model robustness and predictive confidence as proposed by (Lawley et al. 2022). Figure 5 demonstrates an example of a regional-scale prospectivity model designed for the identification of areas with high potential for Mississippi Valley deposit types, as showcased by (Lawley et al. 2022).

Figure 4. Workflow of the regional-scale mineral prospectivity mapping

Weights-of-evidence (WOE) prospectivity results: Mississippi Valley-type (Zn, Pb)

Figure 5. Example of a regional scale mineral prospectivity map for Mississippi Valley-type deposits for (a) the United States and Canada and (b) Australia. Regions that yield high WOE prospectivity scores and low standard deviation (i.e., high confidence) represent the highest priority for mineral exploration targeting (dark yellow) (Reproduced from Lawley et al., 2022)

2.2.2 District Scale Prospectivity Mapping

As the analysis progresses to the district scale, the focus shifts toward refining the regional targets by delineating structurally favourable corridors and prioritising exploration zones. This intermediate scale emphasises the role of major fluid conduits, trap architectures, and proximal source indicators. At this scale, geological and structural maps, as well as more detailed geophysical surveys such as district-scale magnetics, radiometrics, and electromagnetic data, are required. Many of the datasets are available from the Spanish Geological Survey, including geophysical and geochemical data (scale 1:50,000 – 1:200,000).

High-precision geological data (1:50,000) from the Spanish and the Greek Geological Surveys can be acquired, covering parts of the study areas. Analysis of the geological maps revealed several discrepancies and discontinuities between adjacent geological bodies as shown in Figure 6, likely caused by inconsistencies among field surveyors (Bucci et al. 2022). To address these data inconsistencies, automated EO-based mapping approaches will be employed to map the lithology, fault and mineral indicator spatial distribution from multispectral (MS) and hyperspectral (HS) remote sensing data. A detailed description of the automated approaches is provided in Section 3.

Figure 6. A screenshot from the Geological Map of Spain (1:50000 scale) MAGNA 50 showing significant discontinuities between adjacent map sheets around Canteras Mine.

We will use the same approach as in our regional-scale prospectivity mapping, but with higher spatial resolution datasets. Our plan involves developing interpretable ML models that are trained on known mineral occurrences and deposits. These models will help identify metallogenic zones within the areas of the IPB, Granada Basin, and North Evia regions. Additionally, we will implement uncertainty estimation methods to assess the confidence of the district-scale prospectivity mapping model.

Figure 7. Workflow of the district-scale mineral prospectivity mapping.

Figure 8. Example of a district-scale mineral prospectivity map for Cu deposits (reproduced from Mou et al., 2025).

2.2.3 Deposit Scale Prospectivity Mapping

At the deposit scale, where mineral occurrence data are sparse or entirely absent, the workflow transitions to knowledge-driven (Chudasama et al. 2022a) or unsupervised approaches (Chudasama et al. 2022). The modelling objective here is to pinpoint high-potential targets suitable for drilling by characterising key trap zones and fluid conduits at fine resolution. In this context, reliance is placed on expert-derived knowledge of deposit models and mineral system behaviour. An alternative solution is to identify data patterns related to mineralisation in the input feature space and find unexplored regions having the same pattern. In the case of brownfield situations, where mineral deposits and occurrences are known and/or drilling campaigns have been conducted, the prospectivity of the identified regions could be estimated through training ML/DL models with known mineralisation

locations (i.e., coordinates of drilling points showing high mineralisation). The most suitable approach, whether supervised or unsupervised, will be chosen based on the availability of drilling logs. In case no drilling logs are not available, the unsupervised approach demonstrated in Figure 9 will be applied.

Figure 9. Workflow of the deposit-scale mineral prospectivity mapping.

2.3 Architecture of the Mineral Prospectivity Service

The mineral prospectivity mapping will be developed using Python and will incorporate various data from the TerraFusion platform. This process will also utilise lithological, lineament, and mineral indicator/alteration maps provided by the Geological Feature Mapping component of the Raw Material Exploration service (Figure 10). In summary, this service will utilise Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data acquired from CDSE, as well as their corresponding SR versions. Preprocessed geological maps, spaceborne geophysical data, and their derivatives will be available on the TerraFusion platform for analysis through the service. The derived multiscale prospectivity maps, ranging from regional to district to deposit scale, will be stored on the TerraFusion platform as GeoTIFF images.

Figure 10. Functional view of the TERRAVISION Raw Material Exploration Service.

2.4 Future Steps

To advance the implementation of the prospectivity mapping service, the following future steps are planned:

1. **Geological Framework Development:** Gather and synthesise information on the geological formation processes of the targeted deposit types (i.e., VMS, celestine and magnesite deposits). This will support the contextual understanding required for both data-driven and knowledge-based modelling approaches.
2. **Data Collection and Integration:** Acquire and consolidate relevant geospatial, geological, and geophysical datasets at both regional, district and target scales. This includes remote sensing data, surface geology, geophysical data and any existing subsurface data (e.g., drilling logs).
3. **Machine Learning Model Development:** Develop and evaluate interpretable ML models tailored for prospectivity mapping at regional and district scales. Emphasis will be placed on explainability and uncertainty estimation to ensure results are geologically meaningful and actionable.
4. **Addressing Data Scarcity:** Explore and implement strategies to mitigate the challenge of limited training data. Potential approaches include the use of data augmentation method and cost-sensitive learning, objective definition of negative samples (i.e., locations where no mineralisation is expected) and the incorporation of expert knowledge into model development.
5. **Deposit-Scale Prospectivity Mapping:** Based on data availability (e.g., drill core samples, ground-based geophysical surveys), develop either:
 - A **knowledge-based/expert system** where empirical data is insufficient, or

- A **data-driven approach** where high-resolution, localised datasets allow for robust ML model training and validation.

3. Geological Feature Mapping

3.1 Introduction

One of the fundamental steps in mineral exploration is identifying the geological features associated with target ore deposits. These geological features can vary based on the nature of the deposits and may include lithological units, alteration types, tectonic structures, and indicator minerals. When high-quality public geoscience datasets with adequate spatial resolution are unavailable, various geological features can be identified using remote sensing data, employing both knowledge-based and data-driven SOTA methods.

3.2 Lithology Mapping

Spatial information about lithology is essential for exploring mineral resources. Conducting traditional field-based geological surveys often demands significant resources. In response to these limitations, advancements in remote sensing technology have emerged as a valuable alternative, offering a more efficient and accessible approach to geological investigations. Lithological classification using remote sensing stands out for its high processing speed, broad observational scope, and operational efficiency. These advantages have led to its widespread application in large-scale thematic mapping and geological remote sensing surveys.

3.2.1 Methodology

The lithology mapping component will be based on a SOTA method proposed by (Zhang et al. 2024), which makes use of a combination of multisource data (optical, radar, and topographic data, hyperspectral) to provide more comprehensive information and enhanced lithological mapping capabilities. Radar data from Sentinel-1, along with a wide range of VNIR and SWIR optical data from Sentinel-2, Landsat, PRISMA, and EnMAP, as well as Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), will be utilised. Temporally reduced composites of time series of cloud-free data will be produced to minimise the impact of vegetation and land cover changes. This approach helps reduce the effects of clouds and mitigates local spectral distortions, ensuring high-quality, clear, and cloud-free remote sensing data for the entire study area. Finally, the datasets will be resampled to a common spatial resolution of around 5 to 10 m based on the finer spatial resolution data available and will be used to estimate a comprehensive set of input features, including polarisation features, radar texture features, spectral features, optical texture features, PCA features, and topographic features.

The derived features will be fed into an interpretable ML model, which will be trained with lithology samples collected with an automated generation strategy proposed by (Zhang et al. 2024). This method addresses the relationships between various lithological unit boundaries, effectively reducing disputes caused by mixed pixels and significantly enhancing work efficiency. In practice, national geological maps 1:50,000 – 1:200,000 scale will be used as reference to identify the lithology type of the derived samples. The samples will be extracted by first performing principal component analysis (PCA) on the input features, then splitting the extracted principal components into objects with homogeneous feature values with an image segmentation method such as SLIC, SNIC and Multiresolution segmentation. And finally

performing unsupervised clustering on the segments. The final derived clusters that intersect the geological map units will be selected as samples. Finally, the clusters will be shrunk by 500 meters to minimise the risk of placing sample data over ambiguous geological boundaries, where a higher number of mixed pixels is expected.

The methodology incorporates data from multiple sources for lithological mapping, which results in a significant increase in the dimensionality of the features. This, in turn, raises model complexity and the risk of overfitting. To improve efficiency and minimise these risks, a two-step feature selection method will be employed: (1) removing highly correlated predictive features and (2) optimising the model using Recursive Feature Elimination based on interpretable ML models.

Figure 11. Left: Geological map (1:200,000 scale). Right: Lithological mapping results of multi-source remote sensing data. Reproduced from (Zhang et al. 2024).

3.2.2 Architecture of the Lithology Mapping Component

The lithology mapping component will be developed using Python and will incorporate various data from the CDSE, such as Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2, as well as PRISMA, EnMAP, Landsat and enhanced spatial resolution provided by the TerraFusion platform (Figure 12). The derived lithology maps, ranging from regional to deposit scale, will be stored on the TerraFusion platform as GeoTIFF images.

Figure 12. Functional view of the TERRAVISION Lithology Mapping Component.

3.3 Alteration and indicator minerals mapping

Remote sensing plays a crucial role in mapping alteration zones and indicator minerals associated with specific mineralisations.

3.3.1 Methodology

The alteration and indicator mineral mapping component will be based on the “Spectral Hourglass” (Kruse, Boardman, and Huntington 2003) approach, which is a partial spectral unmixing approach to separate minerals between each image pixel. First, the data dimensionality is reduced using the Minimum Noise Fraction (MNF) transform, and then the purest pixels are identified by applying the Pixel Purity Index-Mapping (PPI). Finally, the extracted pure pixels will be grouped into spectrally similar clusters, each representing a different endmember. The extracted endmember will be compared to known spectra from USGS spectral library to further identify and prepare for Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM) classification.

3.3.2 Alteration and indicator mineral service

The alteration and indicator mineral mapping component will be developed using Python and will incorporate data from the CDSE, such as Sentinel-2, as well as PRISMA, EnMAP, Landsat and enhanced spatial resolution provided by the TerraFusion platform (Figure 12). The derived maps, ranging from regional to deposit scale, will be stored on the TerraFusion platform as GeoTIFF images.

Figure 13. Functional view of the TERRAVISION Alteration and Mineral Indicator Mapping Component.

3.4 Lineament Mapping

Geological structures, such as fault and fracture systems, are crucial for the migration, transport, and circulation of metal-bearing hydrothermal fluids. The existence of these structures signifies subsurface structural permeability. It is widely acknowledged that fault and fracture zones are key indicators for identifying favourable locations for hydrothermal

mineral deposits. Therefore, a service component will be developed for lineament mapping using remote sensing images.

3.4.1 Methodology

For automated lineament mapping, the Canny edge detection algorithm will first be applied, followed by the Hough transform to extract linear features from temporally reduced composites of time series Sentinel-1 (VH and VV polarisation), Sentinel-2, and the Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain (MERIT) DEM (Yamazaki et al. 2019) data. The workflow for the extraction of lineaments is depicted in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Workflow of the lineament extraction mapping.

3.4.2 Architecture of the Lineament Mapping Component

The lineament mapping component will be developed using Python and will incorporate data from the CDSE, such as Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, as well as enhanced spatial resolution data such as SR Sentinel-2 and DEM data provided by the TerraFusion platform (Figure 15). The derived maps, ranging from regional to deposit scale, will be stored on the TerraFusion platform as GeoTIFF images and shapefiles.

Figure 15. Functional view of the TERRAVISION Lineament Mapping Component.

3.5 Future Steps

To build on the current progress and improve the service's robustness and applicability, the following future steps are planned:

1. **Implementation and Validation of the Service**

Complete the development and implementation of the lithological, lineament and alteration detection service components.

2. **Feasibility Testing on OpenEO**

Evaluate the deployment feasibility of the developed services on the OpenEO platform to ensure interoperability, scalability, and reproducibility. This step includes testing data processing pipelines and workflow orchestration.

4. Processability Index

4.1 Introduction

The development of a Processability Index (PI) could provide a systematic and quantifiable approach to evaluating the ease or difficulty of processing a specific ore type. The PI is designed as a numerical score derived from mineral group concentrations, providing a quantifiable estimate of ore processability. By integrating mineralogical data with processing implications, the PI will offer a valuable tool for enhancing the efficiency, sustainability and profitability of mining operations.

Defining the processability of ore is fundamental to the success of mineral processing operations, as it determines how efficiently valuable minerals can be extracted from the host rock. Ores that are easier to process typically require less energy, fewer reagents, and simpler processing workflows, resulting in lower operational costs and higher metal recovery rates. Conversely, ores with complex or unfavourable mineralogy may present significant technical challenges, leading to lower yields, increased waste generation, and higher environmental impact. Understanding processability enables more accurate planning for mine scheduling, ore blending, and resource allocation. It also plays a critical role in the economic evaluation of deposits, supporting investment decisions and long-term strategic planning.

4.2 Methodological Framework

The PI methodology is developed using the Tharsis massive sulfide deposit as a representative case study. The methodology is framed within the context of a conventional flotation flowsheet, which includes crushing, milling, and flotation stages. The methodology begins with the identification of typical minerals present in the ore, based on literature sources (Table 1).

Table 1 Typical minerals of Tharsis deposit (Valente et al. 2013).

Silicates	Carbonates	Major Sulfides	Accessory Minerals
Quartz Feldspar Chlorite Plagioclase Sericite Phengite	Siderite Ankerite Calcite	Pyrite Chalcopyrite Sphalerite Galena	Pyrrhotite Marcasite Bornite Covelite Calcosite Tetrahedrite Cobaltite Arsenopyrite Hematite Magnetite Goethite Cassiterite Beudantite

From this mineral inventory, key minerals that significantly influence processing behaviour are selected and grouped into four PI relevant mineral groups (Table 2). Spectral data is then processed to predict the concentration of these minerals within the ore.

Table 2 PI relevant minerals regarding Tharsis deposit.

Gangue1	Gangue2	Detrimental1	Ore1
Quartz	Pyrite	Clay and mica minerals (Dickite, Kaolinite, Nacrite, Montmorillonite, Illite)	Chalcopyrite

Figure 16 Simplified flowsheet of massive sulfide processing.

Each mineral group is classified into four concentration-based classes that reflect different levels of impact on processing (Table 3). For example, chalcopyrite, a primary ore mineral, is more favourable at higher concentrations, while high levels of pyrite or clays are detrimental to flotation performance (Lee, Chen, and Peng 2022). To quantify this impact, each class is assigned a Processability Coefficient, with values ranging from 1.0 to 4.0. These coefficients represent the relative ease or difficulty associated with processing ores containing those mineral concentrations (Table 4).

Table 3 Classification of mineral grades.

Group	Mineral	Class			
		1	2	3	4
Gangue1	Quartz	< 5	5 <= grade < 20	20 <= grade < 50	>50
Gangue2	Pyrite	< 20	20 <= grade < 50	50 <= grade < 80	>80
Detrimental1	Clay and mica minerals	< 2	2 <= grade < 10	10 <= grade < 20	>20
Ore1	Chalcopyrite	< 1.5	1.5 <= grade < 4	4 <= grade < 6	>6

Table 4 Assessed Processability Coefficients.

Mineral Group	Mineral	Class			
		1	2	3	4
Gangue1	Quartz	< 5	5 <= grade < 20	20 <= grade < 50	>50
	Easiness of processability				
	PI Coefficient	4.0	3.0	2.0	1.0
Gangue2	Pyrite	< 20	20 <= grade < 50	50 <= grade < 80	>80
	Easiness of processability				
	PI Coefficient	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0
Detrimental1	Clay and mica minerals	< 2	2 <= grade < 10	10 <= grade < 20	>20
	Easiness of processability				
	PI Coefficient	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0
Ore1	Chalcopyrite	< 1.5	1.5 <= grade < 4	4 <= grade < 6	>6
	Easiness of processability				
	PI Coefficient	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0

4.3 Future Steps

The ultimate goal is to integrate the individual PI coefficients into a composite PI that can be used for automated ore characterisation of the processability. While initially developed for massive sulphide deposits, the approach will be extended to other deposit types with additional ore and gangue minerals and processing schemes as additional data become available.

5. Field Sampling Overview

During the first 18 months of the project, field sampling campaigns were conducted at the Tharsis and Canteras mining sites. These activities were closely coordinated with the airborne data acquisition carried out under Task 5.2. Field samples were collected in the vicinity of the airborne survey flight paths to ensure spatial and contextual alignment between ground-based and remote sensing data. The selection of sampling locations was guided by the need to capture geological diversity and ensure representativeness of the materials present within the surveyed areas. Figures 17, 18 and 19 illustrate the spatial distribution of the collected samples at Canteras site.

Figure 17 Distribution of samples at Canteras Mine.

Figure 18 Distribution of samples at the eastern section of Canteras Mine.

Figure 19 Distribution of samples at the western section of Canteras Mine.

Each sample will undergo systematic laboratory-based spectroscopic and geochemical characterization. Spectral measurements are performed using Near-Infrared (NIR) and Short-Wave Infrared (SWIR) imaging systems to capture spectral signatures. In parallel, geochemical composition was determined using a portable X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) device, providing elemental data essential for cross-validation with spectral information.

In summer/autumn 2025, a final field sampling campaign will be conducted at the TernaMag mining site, in coordination with the planned airborne data acquisition. This campaign will follow the same standardised methodology applied at the previous sites. Samples collected from TernaMag will be analysed using the same NIR and SWIR hyperspectral sensors, along with portable XRF-based geochemical analysis.

6. Conclusion

The report presents an overview of the methodologies that will be developed in the raw material exploration service and the collection of field samples. The SOTA methods for regional, district, and target-scale mineral exploration in greenfield and brownfield areas were identified and modified to meet the project's needs and the availability of the required data. Furthermore, the document outlines the current status of field sampling activities. It also introduces the initial design of the PI, a qualitative metric aimed at characterising ore processing efficiency through spectral-based mineral grade predictions.

The planned next steps are as follows:

- Collection of the required data for the prospectivity mapping.
- Development of the multiscale prospectivity mapping approach.
- Development of an automated approach for characterising ore processability and extension to various deposit types.
- Field mapping on TernaMag is planned to be conducted in September 2025.

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